

[研究文章 Research Article]

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7101070>

First Report of the Family Scirtidae (Insecta: Coleoptera) from Kinmen Island and Lanyu Island, Taiwan

HSING-CHE LIU^{1,*}, CHEN-HAN MA², HIROYUKI YOSHITOMI³

¹ Diversity Ecological Consultant Ltd., No.37, Rende Rd., Taichung City 413, Taiwan.

² Kainan University, No.1, Kainan Rd., Luzhu Dist., Taoyuan City, Taiwan

³ Entomological Laboratory, Faculty of Agriculture, Ehime University, Tarumi 3-5-7, Matsuyama, 790-8566 Japan

* Corresponding author: td965771@gmail.com

Abstract: The beetle family Scirtidae comprises five genera and 15 species in Taiwan. Until now, Scirtidae were not known from the offshore islands of Taiwan. We report the first record of Scirtidae from Kinmen Island and Lanyu Island based on field research and examination of museum collections.

Keywords: new records, *Scirtes japonicus*, aquatic insect, offshore islands, Taiwan

Introduction

The family Scirtidae occur world-wide but are absent from arid areas (Watts & Kwick, 2019). They are common in wetlands where the larvae are mostly aquatic, but all adults are terrestrial insects. Five genera and 15 species are known in Taiwan (Miwa, 1931; Yoshitomi & Satô, 1996, 2004; Yoshitomi, 2001, 2005, 2010, 2012; Ruta, 2010), but until now, all records have been reported from Taiwan Island only.

Since 2020, we have been conducting research on the aquatic insect fauna of offshore islands in Taiwan, including the already published report on aquatic beetles of Penghu Islands (Liu et al., 2020), Dytiscidae and Hydrophilidae of Kinmen Islands and Lanyu Island (Liu et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2021). Based on this research, we have discovered six families of aquatic beetles, and the number of known species has increased from 16 to over 40. In this study, we report Scirtidae from Kinmen Island and Lanyu Island for the first time.

Materials and methods

All specimens were collected using water nets and light traps. Male genitalia were dissected from water-relaxed specimens and examined in temporary glycerine slides without cover glasses. The genitalia were then transferred directly to glycerine for examination. After the examination, the aedeagus was rinsed in 95% alcohol and mounted in Euparal on a small slide below the respective specimen. In some duplicate specimens, the aedeagus was mounted on the same card as the specimen using water-soluble glue. Male genitalia and morphological characters were examined using a Leica DM750 compound microscope.

The materials examined in this paper are deposited at the Department of Entomology, National Chung Hsing University, Taichung City, Taiwan (NCHU: Man-Miao Yang, Sheng-Feng Lin); the first author's collection (HCLC: Hsing-Che Liu's private collection, Hsinchu County, Taiwan) and Ehime University Museum (EUMJ).

Results

Scirtes japonicus Kiesenwetter, 1874

日本圓花蚤

(Fig. 1)

Scirtes japonicus Kiesenwetter, 1874: 244.

Scirtes japonicus: Pic, 1914: 42; Yano et al., 1983: 114 (Tainan).

Material examined. TAIWAN: 5 ex., Hsinchu County, Beipu Township (北埔鄉), N24.70755 E121.06077, 29.III.2019, H.-C. Liu leg. (HCLC); 7 ex., Kinmen Island (金門島), 5–10.VII.2020, In the pond, H.-C. Liu leg. (NCHU, HCLC); 1 ♂, Taitung, Lanyu (蘭嶼), Kaiyuan Port (開元港), N22.059182 E121.509229, 14.V.2021, C.-H. Ma leg, by light (NCHU); 2 ex., Hualien County, Yuli Township (玉里鄉), N23.30001 E121.32647, 1.IV.2022, H.-C. Liu leg. (HCLC); 1 ex., Lanhsu, Taiwan, 5–10.VIII.1998, M. Sato leg. (EUMJ).

Diagnosis. Body length 3.8–4.3 mm. Body elongate, dorsal surface darker brown (Fig. 1A, C); Metatibia are rather well developed; Median lobe slightly longer than parameres, wide basally, narrowing at apex, but slightly rounded at ca.1/9; parameres very slender (Fig. 1B).

Distribution. This species is widely distributed in Eastern Asia, Hawaii Islands; it is a common species at low altitude in Taiwan (Yano et al., 1983; Yoshitomi, 2005, 2008), Kinmen Island. (new record) and Lanyu Island. (new record).

Bionomics. This species inhabits stagnant water pools with rich aquatic plants (Fig. 1D). Some specimens can be collected from light traps.

Figure 1. *Scirtes japonicus*. A – dorsal habitus; B – male genitalia, dorsal view; C – living individual, photo from Lanyu Island, photo by C.-H. Ma; D – habitat, from Kinmen Island.

Acknowledgements

The first author is grateful to the Laboratory of Urban Entomology, Department of Entomology, National Chung Hsing University, including Hou-Feng Li and Chia-Chien Wu, for providing photographic equipment. We are indebted to two anonymous reviewers who helped to improve this manuscript a lot.

References

Kiesenwetter, H. von. 1874. Die Malacodermes Japans nach dem Ergebnisse der Sammlungen des Herrn G. Lewis während der Jahre 1869–1871. *Berliner Entomologische Zeitschrift* 18 (3-4): 241–288.

- Liu, H. -C., Lin, J. -H. & Zheng, K. -Y. 2020. Notes on Water Beetle (Insecta: Coleoptera) of Penghu Islands, Taiwan. *Taiwanese Journal of Entomological Studies* 5 (4): 49–60. (in Chinese)
- Liu, H. -C., Ma, C. -H. & Fikáček, M. 2021. Water scavenger beetles of Kinmen County, Taiwan (Coleoptera: Hydrophilidae). *Taiwan Journal of Biodiversity* 23 (1): 39–62.
- Liu, H. -C., Ma, C. -H., Fikáček, M. & Wang, L. -J. 2021. Annotated catalogue of the water scavenger beetles from Orchid Island, Taiwan (Coleoptera: Hydrophilidae). *Japanese Journal of Systematic Entomology* 27 (2): 301–309.
- Miwa, Y. 1931. A systematic catalogue of Formosan Coleoptera. *Report of the Government Research Institute, Department of Agriculture, Taihoku, Formosa* 55: 1–359.
- Pic, M. 1914. Pars 58. Dascillidae, Helodidae, Eucinetidae. pp 1–65. In: Schenkling S. (eds). *Coleopterorum Catalogus*. W. Junk, Berlin.
- Ruta, R. 2010. Two new species of *Prionocyphon* Redtenbacher from Taiwan (Coleoptera: Scirtidae), with notes on *Prionocyphon*, *Mescirtes* Motschulsky and *Prionoscirtes* Champion from East and Southeast Asia. *Zootaxa* 2402 (1): 52–60.
- Wang, L. -J., Hendrich, L. & Balke, M. 2021. First records of the diving beetles *Hydrovatus subrotundatus* Motschulsky, 1859 and *Hydrovatus pudicus* (Clark, 1863) in Taiwan (Coleoptera, Dytiscidae, Hydroporinae, Hydrovatini). *Check List* 17 (5): 1295–1298.
- Watts, C. H. S. & Zwick, P. 2019. 15. SCIRTIDAE FLEMING, 1821. pp 221–248. In: Slipinski A., Lawrence J. (eds). *Australian Beetles: Archostemata, Myxophaga, Adephaga, Polyphaga (part)*, Vol. 2. CSIRO Publishing, Victoria.
- Yano, K., Chu, Y. -I., Resma, P. W. & Satô, M. 1983. Faunal and biological studies on the insects of paddy fields in Asia. XII. Aquatic Coleoptera from Taiwan and the Philippines. *Chinese Journal of Entomology* 3 (2): 103–118.
- Yoshitomi, H. 2001. Taxonomic study on the genus *Hydrocyphon* (Coleoptera, Scirtidae) of Japan and her adjacent regions. *Elytra, Tokyo* 29 (1): 87–107.
- Yoshitomi, H. 2005. Systematic revision of the family Scirtidae of Japan, with phylogeny, morphology and bionomics (Insecta: Coleoptera, Scirtoidea). *Japanese Journal of Systematic Entomology, Monographic Series* 3: 1–212.
- Yoshitomi, H. 2008. *Scirtes japonicus* (Coleoptera, Scirtidae): new records from the Hawaii Islands. *The Coleopterists Bulletin* 62 (2): 278.
- Yoshitomi, H. 2010. A new species of the genus *Prionocyphon* from Taiwan (Coleoptera: Scirtidae: Scirtinae). *Acta Entomologica Musei Nationalis Pragae* 50 (2): 529–533.
- Yoshitomi, H. 2012. A new species of the genus *Sacodes* Leconte from Taiwan (Coleoptera, Scirtidae). *Koleopterologische Rundschau* 82: 301–305.
- Yoshitomi, H. & Satô, M. 1996. Two new species of the genus *Flavohelodes* (Coleoptera, Scirtidae) from Taiwan. *Elytra, Tokyo* 24 (2): 303–309.
- Yoshitomi, H. & Satô, M. 2004. Scirtidae of the Oriental Region, Part 7. A new species of the genus *Sacodes* (Coleoptera, Scirtidae) from Taiwan. *Japanese Journal of Systematic Entomology* 10 (2): 211–214.

臺灣金門島及蘭嶼的圓花蚤科（昆蟲綱：鞘翅目）首次報告

劉興哲^{1,*}、馬承漢²、吉富博之³

¹ 多樣性生態顧問有限公司 413 臺中市霧峰區仁德巷 12 弄 37 號

² 開南大學 桃園市蘆竹區開南路 1 號

³ 愛媛大学 農学部 昆虫学研究室 790-8566 日本松山市樽味 3 丁目 5 番 7 号

* 通訊作者：td965771@gmail.com

摘要：圓花蚤科在臺灣已知 5 屬 15 種，但臺灣離島尚未有圓花蚤科的報導。本研究根據實地考察和博物館標本檢查，首次報導金門群島和蘭嶼的圓花蚤科紀錄。

關鍵字：新紀錄、日本圓花蚤、水棲昆蟲、離島、臺灣